

IPBES IAS assessment, Chapter 4. Figure 4.27: Synthesis of cumulative economic costs of biological invasions

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Description

Figure 4.27 synthesises the cumulative economic costs of biological invasions as available in the literature and standardized in the InvaCost database (latest version 4.0 available at the time of writing this report): for all countries in the world, the 10 countries with the highest cumulative costs and the four major taxonomic groups, as well as the ten costliest taxa. Note that this figure represents data recorded in the latest version of the InvaCost database available at the time of writing this report, and then the proportions displayed here are likely to evolve as the database is updated over time. All cost information is regularly updated (Leroy et al., 2021 for the most up-to-date figures).

Process overview

We used the *Approach based on available estimates* provided and explained in the Invacost package available here <https://github.com/Farewe/invacost>.

All costs have been standardized in equivalent 2017 US\$ (Diagne, Leroy, et al. (2021) and Leroy et al. (2022) for methodological details) and only the most robust subset has been used here.

Protocol

1. Map of all cumulative cost of biological invasions per country (1970-2020)

Code: Cost_map.R

Datasets:

- Geo_High_Observed.txt
- IPBES region and subregion data.csv

2. Top 10 Countries with highest cumulative cost

- Dataset: Geo_High_Observed.txt

3. Four major taxonomic groups

- Dataset: IPBES_Invacost_Dataset.csv (high confidence data retrieved from the Invacost Database on 8 July 2022)

4. Ten costliest taxa

- Dataset: IPBES_Invacost_Dataset.csv (high confidence data retrieved from the Invacost Database on 8 July 2022)

Files:

- Cost_map.R
- Geo_High_Observed.txt
- IPBES region and subregion data.csv
- IPBES_Invacost_Dataset.csv